

In-vitro Characterization and Anti-microbial Activity of Imidazole Derivatives

Dr. Santosh Prajapati¹, Shobha Sahu*¹, Mohini Kashyap², Mendra Kumar³, Jharna Sahu⁴, Divya Pandey²

¹Columbia Institute of Pharmacy, Tekari – 493111, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India

²Danteshwari College of Pharmacy, Borpadar – 494221, Jagdalpur, Chhattisgarh, India

³Mona College of Pharmacy, Sarangarh – 495551, Chhattisgarh, India

⁴Bharti College of Pharmacy, Durg – 491001, Chhattisgarh, India

Abstract:

Overuse and misuse of antibiotics create superbugs as drug-resistant bacteria. The vital strategy is developing new antibiotics, and one of the vital compounds that proved activity as antimicrobials is imidazoles. So, we designed and synthesized a series of oxazole and their imidazole derivatives were prepared from 6-bromo-2-chloro-3-formylquinoline. The structures of all the synthesized compounds were elucidated by elemental, IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR spectra. They were assayed in vitro for their antimicrobial activity. It was revealed that some synthesized derivatives show remarkable biological activity against both gram-negative and gram-positive bacterial species and fungal microorganisms. The results obtained from spectroscopic analyses approved the chemical structures of new compounds. The biological antimicrobial activity result was found that these compounds exert an excellent broad spectrum antimicrobial activity against many Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as different fungal strain including some highly human pathogenic microorganisms.

Keywords: Imidazole; Anti-bacterial activity; Microbial assay

1. Introduction

The imidazole derivatives have occupied a unique place in the field of medicinal chemistry due to their diverse pharmacological activities such as anti-microbial, anti-cancer, anti-viral anti-tubercular and anti-inflammatory activity. [1] In this context, a variety of methods for synthesis of imidazoles have been developed. However, many of the reported protocols suffer from several disadvantages such as high catalyst loading, strong acidic conditions, low yield, high temperature, prolonged reaction times, cumbersome methodology, eco-hazards and complexity in product isolation. To circumvent these problems, now-a-days natural substances are increasingly used in organic syntheses for their safety aspects towards the environment. [2-3] Herein, an organo-catalyzed one-pot cyclocondensation of ammonium acetate, 1, 2-diphenyl ethanedione, aromatic aldehyde in ethanol is developed to form 2,4,5 tri-substituted imidazole derivatives in good to excellent yields in a short reaction time. The method is greener, economical and metal

free for the synthesis of multi-substituted imidazole derivatives, promoted by naturally occurring organo-catalysts. [4] The synthesized imidazole derivatives will be screened for their antibacterial activity. bacterial infection has been resulted development of a wide variety of antibiotics. After years of misuse and overuse of antibiotics, bacteria are becoming antibiotic resistant, resulting in a potential global health crisis. Frequently, it is recommended to use new antibacterial agents with enhanced broad-spectrum potency. Therefore, recent efforts have been directed towards exploring novel antibacterial agents. [5-6] Apart from this, during the past 20 years an increase of invasive microbial infections has been observed The use of small organic molecules as catalysts has gained increasing importance recently. These substances, the so-called organocatalysts, present a lot of advantages, like being less toxic, less polluting, and more economically viable than the organometallic catalysts that dominate asymmetric synthesis. [7] Organocatalysis can be greener than traditional catalysis because. The use of catalyst consequently saving energy. It uses, in general, oxygen-stable reagents and does not require anhydrous conditions, reducing the cost of the synthesis. It is compatible with several functional groups. It uses less toxic and safer substances. Example of organocatalyst are thiourea, proline, phenylalanine , aspartic acid and ascorbic acid. [8-9]

Imidazole

Imidazole is an organic compound with the formula $C_3N_2H_4$. It is a white or colorless solid that is soluble in water, producing a mildly alkaline solution. In chemistry, it is an aromatic heterocycle, classified as a diazole, and has non-adjacent nitrogen atoms. Many natural products, especially alkaloids, contain the imidazole ring. [10] These imidazoles share the 1,3- C_3N_2 ring but feature varied substituents. This ring system is present in important biological building blocks, such as histidine and the related hormone histamine. Many drugs contain an imidazole ring, such as certain antifungal drugs, the nitro-imidazole series of antibiotics, and the sedative midazolam. [11] When fused to a pyrimidine ring, it forms a purine, which is the most widely occurring nitrogen-containing heterocycle in nature. The name "Imidazole" was coined in 1887 by the German chemist Arthur Rudolf Hantzsch (1857–1935). [12]

Structure and properties of imidazole

Imidazole is a monoacidic base having the ability to form crystalline salts with acids. The melting point of number of characteristic imidazolium salts Imidazole is a 5-membered planar ring, which is soluble in water and other polar solvents. It exists in two equivalents Tautomeric forms, 1H-imidazole and 3H-imidazole, because the hydrogen atom can be located on either of the two nitrogen atoms. [13-14] Imidazole is a highly polar compound, as evidenced by a calculated dipole of 3.61D, and is entirely soluble in water. The compound is classified as aromatic due to the presence of a sextet of p-electrons, consisting of a pair of electrons from the protonated nitrogen atom and one from each of the remaining four atoms of the ring. [15]

Reactivity

Imidazole can be considered as having properties similar to both pyrrole and pyridine. The electrophilic reagent would attack the unshared electron pair on N-3, but not that on the 'pyrrole' nitrogen since it is the part of the aromatic sextet. While the imidazole ring is rather susceptible to electrophilic attack on an annular carbon, it is much less likely to become involved in nucleophilic substitution reaction unless there is a strongly electron withdrawing substituent's elsewhere in the ring. [16] In the absence of such activation the

position most prone to nucleophilic attack is C-2. The fused benzene ring in benzimidazole provides sufficient electron withdrawal to allow a variety of nucleophilic substitution reaction at C-2. [17] The overall reactivity of imidazoles and benzimidazole is referred from sets of resonance structure in which the dipolar contributors have finite importance. These predict electrophilic attack in imidazole at N-3 or any ring carbon atom, nucleophilic attack at C-2 or C-1 and also the amphoteric nature of the molecule. In benzimidazole the nucleophilic attack is predicted at C-2. The reactivity of benzimidazole ion at the C-2 position with nucleophiles is enhanced compared with the neutral molecule. [18-19]

Physical properties

It is colorless liquid having a high B.P. of 256 °C than all other 5-membered heterocyclic compounds due to the intermolecular H-bonding, where there is linear association of molecule. Imidazoles show a large value of dipole moment of 4.8 D in dioxane. Imidazole show amphoteric properties and has pKa of 7.2 more than pyrazole and pyridine. [20] Imidazoles are an aromatic compound possessing a resonance value of 14.2 K cal/ mol, which is almost half the value for pyrazole. The electrophilic substitution occurs frequently in imidazole and nucleophilic substitution happens in the presence of electron withdrawing group in its nucleus. Imidazoles have M.P. 90°C, it is a weak base and tautomeric substance, since position 4 and 5 are equivalent. [21]

It's spectroscopic parameters are λ_{\max} of 207 nm, I.R.=1550, 1492, 1451(cm^{-1}), $t = 2.30, 2.86$, mass spectroscopy is studied for heterocyclic compounds containing one hetero-atom, in detail, not in case containing two or more heteroatom. [22]

2. Materials and Methods

Based on the interesting biological importance of imidazole derivatives as mentioned above, we are interested to develop a novel greener method to synthesize imidazole derivative. [23]

Table 1. List of chemicals.

S. No.	Name of chemical	Name of company
1.	Ascorbic acid	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
2.	Acetone	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
3.	Hexane	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
4.	Sodium hydroxide	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
5.	Ethanol	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
6.	Methanol	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
7.	Iodine	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
8.	Phenylalanine	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
9.	Proline	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
10.	Benzil	Hi Media Laboratory Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai India
11.	Ammonium acetate	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
12.	Vanillin	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
13.	2-chlorobenzeldehyde	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
14.	Benzeldehyde	Loba chemie pvt, Ltd, Mumbai , India
15.	Salicyladehyde	Hi Media Laboratory Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai India

Table 2. List of instruments.

S. No.	Name of instrument	Name of company
1.	Analytical digital weight balance	Keroy KRT , kero (balance) pvt. Ltd. Varanasi
2.	Heating mantle	Suntek
3.	Distillation condenser	Borosil
4.	Rota evaporator	Buchi
5.	Hot air oven	Radical scientific equipments private Ltd.
6.	Autoclave	Labline
7.	NMR	Bruker 500MHz
8.	MASS analyzer	(ESI-MS) agilent LC-QTOF

3. Results

Optimization of reaction

Table 3. Optimization of various reaction parameters for the synthesis of imidazole.

Entry	catalyst	mol %	Solvent	Temperature	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1.	Aspartic acid	1	EtOH	rt	24	0
2.	Aspartic acid	5	EtOH	65	12	58
3.	Aspartic acid	5	EtOH	75	12	60
4.	Proline	5	EtOH	65	4	92

5.	Proline	5	EtOH	75	4	90
6.	Proline	3	EtOH	65	4	82
7.	Proline	10	EtOH	65	4	92
8.	Phenyl alanine	5	EtOH	65	4	40
9.	Urea	5	EtOH	65	4	00
10.	Ascorbic acid	5	EtOH	65	4	22
11.	Proline	5	water	65	24	Trace
12.	Proline	5	THF	65	4	55
13.	Proline	5	Toluene	65	4	20

Herein we wish to report a remarkable activity of proline to catalyze multi-component reaction to afford imidazole derivatives in high yields and purity. To the best of our knowledge proline has not been previously reported for the preparation of imidazoles. Initially, we screened the reaction conditions for the synthesis of substituted imidazoles by using benzaldehyde, benzil and ammonium acetate in presence of 1 mol % of proline. [24] Product formation was not observed at room temperature even after 24 h (Table 1, entry 1). However, the reaction treated with 5 mol% of proline gave desired product in 58% yield after 12 h (Table 1, entry 2). Elevated temperature did not give promising outcome (Table 1, entry 3). Fascinatingly, complete conversion of starting material took place and gave 92% yield of product in 4 h, when the reaction was carried out by switching the catalyst to proline (5 mol %) (Table 1, entry 4). In an attempt to improve the yield, the reaction was repeated with high temperature, but there is no improvement in yield or time (Table 1, entry 5). [25] The reaction was also investigate by reducing the catalyst loading, less yield of the product was observed (Table 1, entry 6). Moreover, increasing the catalyst loading did not improve the product yield (Table 1, entry 7). We next examined other organocatalyst such as phenylalanine, urea and ascorbic acid, but the results were not promising (Table 1, entries 8-10). We also tried reaction in water, THF and toluene, but the yields of the desired products were inferior (Table 1, entries 11-13). Thus, 5 mol% of proline and EtOH were selected as the optimized condition for synthesis of imidazoles (Table 1, entry 4). The confirmation of 2,4,5-triphenyl-1*H*-imidazole was done by mass spectrometry and ¹H NMR, where m/z at 297 and δ value at aromatic region confirmed the formation of product. [26-27]

Synthesis of imidazole derivative

Cyclocondensation of 1 Benzil, aldehydes (2-chlorobenzaldehyde, vanillin, benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, 4pyridine carboxaldehyde) 2, ammonium acetate in methanol using 5 mol % proline . after 3 hrs. cold water added then leave for 15 minut so that precipitated of the compound then filter the solution , wash with distilled leave for drying then solvent wash with 1% of ethyl acetate + hexane , dry the product , stored in closed container. In this reaction using proline reagent having analytical grade and more than 98% purity ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded using CDCl_3 and $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ as solvent purity of compound chacked by TLC. [28-30]

Synthesis of 2-(2-chlorophenyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazole

It was observed that, by using 5 mol % of proline in solution of 2-chloro benzaldehydes (1 equiv), benzil (1 equiv) and ammonium acetate (4 equiv) in EtOH at 65 °C was easily afforded desired substituted imidazoles in admirable yields (90%). [31] The confirmation of the product was done by Mass spectrum, where m/z at 331 ($M+H$)⁺ showed the formation of desired product have molecular mass 330. Further confirmation was done by ¹H NMR in which the δ value at aromatic region evidenced the presence of 2-chlorophenyl ring in the structure of desired product. [32]

Fig.1. [2-(2-chlorophenyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazole]

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR of 2-(2-chlorophenyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazole.

Synthesis of 5-(4, 5-diphenyl-1H -imidazole-2-yl) 2 methoxy phenol.

When vanillin was treated with equimolar quantity of benzil and 4 equiv of ammonium acetate, under the present reaction conditions resulted in 96% yield of the desired product. [33-34] We confirm the product by ¹H NMR, where δ value at aromatic region conform the presence of OMe proton in vanillin moiety. Moreover mass spectrum displayed m/z at 343 confirmed the formation of product (table 2).

Fig. 3. [5-(4, 5-diphenyl-1H -imidazole-2-yl) 2 methoxy phenol].

Fig. 4. ¹H NMR of 5-(4, 5-diphenyl-1H -imidazole-2-yl) 2 methoxy phenol.

Synthesis of 4-(4, 5- diphenyl- 1H-imidazole-2-yl) pyridine.

Cyclocondation reaction of 1mole of benzil , 1 mole benzaldehyde , 3 mole ammonium acetate presence of proline organocatalyst in ethanol solvent give 90% yield at 65°C in 2hrs formation product 4-(4,5- diphenyl- 1H-imidazole-2-yl)pyridine , molecular formula C₂₀H₁₅N₃, molecular weight 297 white colour. (table 2). [35-36]

Fig.5. [4-(4,5- diphenyl- 1H-imidazole-2-yl)pyridine]

Fig.6. ^1H NMR of 4-(4,5- diphenyl- 1H-imidazole-2-yl)pyridine.

Synthesis of 2-(4, 5-diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl) phenol

Similarly, salicylaldehyde reacted well under the optimized reaction conditions with benzil and ammonium acetate to afford desired product in excellent yield (92%). The formed product was characterized by ^1H NMR, where δ value at aromatic region confirmed the presence of OH group. [37-38] Furthermore mass analysis displayed the m/z at 313 gives the further support for the formation of desired product (table2)

Fig.7. [2-(4, 5-diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl) phenol]

Fig.8. ¹HNMR of 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)phenol.

Table 4. Compound are characterize by mass that list below.

S. No	Compounds	Molecular Formula	Mw	Color
1.	2-(2-chlorophenyl)-4,5 diphenyl-1H-imidazole .	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ ClN ₂	331	Pale white
2.	5-(4,5-diphenyl-1H -imidazole-2-yl) 2 methoxy phenol.	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	343	Brown
3.	4-(4,5- diphenyl- 1H-imidazole-2-yl) pyridine.	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃	297	White
4.	2-(4,5-diphenyl -1H-imidazole-2-yl) phenol.	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	313	Brown

Microbial assay of synthesis compound

Collection of Bacteria

Culture tube was sterilize then sterile nutrition broth was added in culture tube. few mg of gram positive and gram negative bacteria was added on culture tube containing nutrient broth tied the cap stored in incubator for 18-24 hours. [39]

Fig.9. Bacteria culture solution.

Preparation of drug dilution

All volumetric flask and glassware was sterilized by hot air oven. Dilution of standard drug - amoxicillin from 200 - 1000 micro gram per ml. was prepared. Further same dilution of imidazole derivative. Disk was dipped on drug dilution. [40-41]

Fig.10. Microbial assay.

Experimental for antibacterial assay

Firstly all glassware - petridish, volumetric flask, glass rod, sterilized by autoclave. Where practical performed cleaned by ethanol. Disk sterilized by autoclave. Agar media prepared. [42-43] Then autoclave for 20 minute in 15 LBS. Transfer the sterile agar solution on petridish then immediate cover the plate. Make 5 zone by marker. Spread the culture media on petridish by sterile cotton bud. Transfer the disk on petridish. Cover the petridish. Then leave for 18 hrs in incubator for their inhibition control. [44-45]

Evaluation zone inhibition

Value of amoxicillin and imidazole derivative was calculated. Zone inhibition was compared.

Fig.11. (a) Standard drug zone inhibition bacteria. **(b)** Synthesize drug zone inhibition of bacteria.

Table 5. Antibacterial activity of drug and their zone inhibition calculation.

Species	Concentration Micro gram per ml	Enterobacter aerogenes	bacillus cereus	agrobacterium tumefacines	Streptococcus pyonees
1st drug 1a	200	Not active	Not active	Not active	Not active
1b	400	–	–	–	–
1c	600	–	–	–	–
1d	800	–	–	–	–
1e	1000	–	–	–	–
Amoxicillin 1A	200	Not active	Not active	Not active	Not active
1B	400	1.7	1.5	1.6	–
1C	600	1.7	1.7	1.8	1

1D	800	2.1	2.4	1.4	1.7
1E	1000	2.5	2.6	1.5	2
2nd drug 2a	200	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.8
2b	400	0.5	0.4	0.6	0.9
2c	600	0.7	0.5	0.7	1.1
2d	800	0.9	0.6	0.8	1.3
2e	1000	1.2	0.7	0.88	1.6
Amoxicillin 2A	200	1.23	2	1	0.6
2B	400	2.25	2.3	1	0.68
2C	600	2.5	2.4	1	1.08
2D	800	3	2.5	1.05	1.9
2E	1000	3.3	3	1.9	2.1

3rd drug	200	0.6	0.5	0.9	0.5
3a					
3b	400	0.7	0.5	0.95	0.7
3c	600	0.9	0.65	1.4	1.2
3d	800	0.95	0.69	1.45	1.5
3e	1000	1.1	1.07	1.9	1.9
Amoxicillin	200	0.6	1.8	2.17	2.5
3A					
3B	400	0.65	2.1	2.6	2.9
3C	600	0.7	2.4	2.8	2.9
3D	800	0.8	2.7	3.3	3.2
3E	1000	1	3.2	3.9	3.7
4th drug	200	0.4	0.57	0.6	0.5

4a					
4b	400	0.42	1	0.7	1.0
4c	600	0.6	1.3	0.8	1.5
4d	800	0.8	1.72	1.05	1.7
4e	1000	1.4	2.6	1.4	2.7
Amoxicillin	200	2.4	0.8	1	0.5
4A					
4B	400	2.7	0.9	1.1	0.6
4C	600	3.0	1.8	1.2	0.65
4D	800	3.1	2.1	1.8	0.7
4E	1000	3.6	2.5	2.7	1.85

Therapeutic effectiveness

1st synthesized drug 2-(2-chlorophenyl)-4,5 diphenyl-1H-imidazole was very less antibacterial activity against all bacteria & 200 mg/ml amoxicillin less active in all bacteria. [46-47] 2nd synthesized drug 5-(4, 5-diphenyl-1H -imidazole-2-yl) 2 methoxy phenol was antibacterial activity against all bacteria but less than amoxicillin. 3rd synthesized drug 4-(4, 5- diphenyl- 1H-imidazole-2-yl) pyridine was antibacterial activity against all bacteria, equipotent activity against E.aerogenes. 4th synthesis drug 2-(4, 5-diphenyl -1H-imidazole-2-yl) phenol was good antibacterial activity against all bacteria & same equipotent activity as amoxicillin But this synthesized drug was more active than amoxicillin against Streptococcus pyonees. [48-49]

4. Discussion

Initially study has been started with screening of solvents in one-pot reaction 1 equivalent benzaldehyde 1 equivalent ammonium acetate and 4 equivalent proline catalyst. Reaction was efficiently promoted in ethanol according to screening results as compared to other catalysts (Table 1). Above screening results revealed that the solvent plays a key role in this transformation. For instance, a best yield was obtained when ethanol was utilized good in 65 temp. At 2 hrs give 90% yield. (Table1) ethanol is an eco-friendly, cheaper, safe solvent and preferred as medium for clean synthesis. different catalysts and results are good yield was obtained in the presence of L-proline . However, other catalysts (such as urea, aspartic acid, ascorbic acid, phenyl alanine have been afforded moderate yield with higher reaction time. In the screening part, we have examined acids, amine and metal salt as catalysts. However, all catalysts showed some activity but were not efficient. L-Proline has dual functionality and both free NH and COOH groups of L-proline are essential for efficient transformation. L- Proline easily form minium complex, this may be due the fact that protonation of amine moiety of catalyst which subsequent easily react with aldehyde. Protonation of amine may be easily achieved dipolar structure of acid and amine resultant high yield was obtained due to combine effect of acid and amine moiety. Rest of catalysts have not this dual functionality or nature to catalyze the reaction efficiently results low yield was achieved. The reaction was then conducted at different time interval, such as using ethanol solvent at different temp and time 24 temp. In 4 hrs give 0% yield , 25temp. In 5 hrs give 20% yield, 50 temp in 6hrs give 40% yield , 65 temp in 2hrs give 90% yield in table 1. There are few reports in literature for synthesis of 3,4-dihydro-1H-chromeno[4,3-d]pyrimidine-2,5-dione/thione derivatives using 4-hydroxy coumarin, aldehydes and urea/thiourea in the presence of homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts. Reported methods show that researchers has used catalyst such as urea , aspartic acid , ascorbic acid , phenylalanine which has drawbacks such as longer reaction time, harsh reaction conditions. Urea can be irritating to skin eyes and respiratory tract, aspartic acid has an acidic side chain which react react with other amino acid, enzyme and proteins in body. ascorbic acid include transient mild soreness. Phenylalanine can cause intellectual disabilities, brain damage , seizure and other problem in people with Phenylketonuria. Firstly reaction with 2 chlorobenzaldehyde so that compound formed 2-(2-chlorophenyl)4,5 diphenyl-1H-imidazole their molecular formula $C_{21}H_{15}ClN_2$ and molecular weight 331 and color found pale white. 2nd reaction with vanillin give 5-(4,5-diphenyl-1H -imidazole-2-yl) 2 methoxy phenol, molecular formula $C_{22}H_{18}N_2O_2$ mw 347 brown color. 3rd reaction with benzaldehyde give 4-(4,5- diphenyl- 1H-imidazole-2-yl)pyridine. , $C_{20}H_{15}N_3$ and mw 297 white color. 4th reaction with salisaldehyde give 2-(4,5-diphenyl -1H-imidazole-2-yl)phenol their molecular formula $C_{21}H_{16}N_2O$ and mw 313 brown color show in table-2 were all characterize by NMR spectra.

5. Conclusion

We have developed an efficient one-pot method for the synthesis of multi-substituted imidazole derivatives in the presence of proline as a green catalyst in good yields from readily available starting materials. The catalytic activity of proline remarkable and another advantage of using of it as a novel promoter for this transformation is its green property under the aspect of environmentally benign processes. This improved modified method for preparation of multi-substituted imidazole derivatives is a simple, high-yielding, timesaving, environmentally benign and user-friendly process. Furthermore, the investigations of biological activities clearly indicate that most of imidazole derivatives show good anti-bacterial activity. The synthesized compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity, in which compound 2 was found to be most active against enterobacteria aerogenous (table 3).

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